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Towards a general tool chain integration platform for multi-disciplinary analysis and optimization in wind energy

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Abstract. To enable easier uptake and flexible usage for the wind energy community, a general tool chain integration platform for multi-disciplinary analysis and optimization, TopDesign, is proposed and developed. This work describes its concept and the initial implementation. The platform is written in Python and provided as an open source framework. The design of this platform puts emphasis on flexibility, usability and extensibility. General model classes with standard interfaces, which can wrap custom tools/models in different formats based on different programming languages, will be provided together with examples that are easy to understand and modify. Coupling tools/models into a system thus becomes an easy task of connecting models by inputs and outputs and defining workflow with a directed graph. To demonstrate the usage of the proposed platform, we implement a wind farm evaluation system by coupling the PyWake model, the FLORIS model and self-written constraint models in the platform and apply it in solving wind farm layout optimization problems with two algorithms, as implemented in an in-house optimization Python library. A case study for a wind farm composed of 9 turbines shows the potential of the proposed platform and methodology.

1. Introduction

Researchers and engineers in wind energy need to solve various multi-disciplinary analysis and optimization (MDAO) problems, such as design optimization of wind turbines [1] and wind farms [2]. This requires them to use different tools or models and couple them together to form some sort of systems. Since these tools or models are usually written with different programming languages, take different formats and are developed by different groups and/or companies, this is not an easy task. In a broader context, formal methodology such as model-based systems engineering (MBSE) [3] has gained growing popularity in the development of complex engineering systems, which relies more and more on computational models as the central workforces. However, how to better integrate and couple different tools or models for a specific application field is still an important question to consider for anyone trying to solve MDAO problems.

In the past decades, multiple general purpose MDAO platforms with different focuses, like DAKOTA [4] and OpenMDAO [5], have been developed from different engineering backgrounds. They can also be used to solve MDAO problems in the wind energy field. However, using them effectively requires substantial learning and development efforts. Also, sometimes, the focus of the existing platforms does not suit the current needs in wind energy MDAO so well. For example, OpenMDAO is gradient-based optimization oriented and works very efficiently in that setting, but can be difficult to include flexible and discontinuous workflows, like conditionally/adaptively switching between different

models in the optimization process. Thus, there is a need for an open source platform that is developed for MDAO in wind energy that can:

- easily integrate/couple different models/tools in different formats and programming languages;
- include other platform (like OpenMDAO) based models/systems as subsystems;
- enable flexible and discontinuous workflows like switching between different models/settings on the fly during optimization processes;
- be configured and applied to various kinds of MDAO tasks in wind energy;
- be easily extended, adapted and maintained by different users from both academia and industry, thus be readily absorbed by the wind energy sector.

To fulfil this need, we present in this study the design of a general tool chain integration platform for MDAO in wind energy, which is currently named as TopDesign, and demonstrate its usage for wind farm optimization problems. In this example, two popular open source wind farm simulation tools, PyWake [6] and FLORIS [7], are wrapped and coupled with self-written wind farm constraint models to form an integrated wind farm evaluation system. Then this system is used by optimization algorithms to optimize the wind farm layout with regards to the considered objective function and constraints. A case study on a wind farm with 9 large wind turbines demonstrates the effectiveness of the proposed platform and methodology.

2. Integration platform and methodology

To be able to couple and integrate different models and tools, we develop a general platform with Python using an objective-oriented programming methodology. These tools or models don't have to be Python based but can be written in different languages (like Matlab, Fortran, C++) and take different formats (like scripts, compiled executables). Depending on the usage scenarios, these tools or models can also be open source or commercial, in-house developed or third-party provided.

In this platform, to enable smooth coupling and interactions, any existing customer tool/model is embedded/wrapped into a Python object representing the model. For a newly developed tool/model, it is also required to have the standard interfaces. Figure 1 shows the concept of the proposed general Python model.

Figure 1. A general Python model which embeds/wraps other customer model

This general model contains:

- (1) **inputs** that get into the model and may come from another model;
- (2) **outputs** that get out of the model and may go into another model;
- (3) **parameters** that may be provided to specify/adapt the setting of the model;
- (4) **customer model** that is embedded/wrapped and does the actual computation of the model;
- (5) **state recorder** that stores the history of the model evaluations, like a list of inputs and outputs pairs that have been computed.

Note that the customer model may not be presented in the general model if the whole model is written in Python and follows the format and interfaces as shown in Figure 1. In the current implementation, the data structure `dictionary` in Python is used to define the inputs and outputs of a model, which requires the specification of names for all variables as key words. Thus, clearly naming and matching these variables in the inputs and outputs will be crucial for enabling the smooth coupling and integration of different models.

With all the relevant tools/models wrapped into different Python models, they can then be integrated/coupled into a system to carry out a multi-disciplinary analysis. As a generic example, Figure 2 shows a system that integrates/couples 6 models. The workflow, i.e., the order of executing different models and coupling inputs and outputs, is defined by a directed graph. Also there can be selectors and adaptors between models to enable a more flexible and adaptive workflow. Complex logic can also be embedded in the implementation of the system, which could be beneficial for solving complex engineering problems.

Comparing Figure 2 with Figure 1, one can notice the similarity of a system with a model, i.e., both transform inputs to output with state recorder and optional parameters. In fact, in the implementation of the platform, the `System` class is defined as a child class of `Model`. Thus, the design of the general set up of a system/model enables us to treat a system as a model and construct a complex system by coupling/integrating different subsystems, models/tools in a hierarchical and nested way.

Figure 2. A system coupling multiple models with a directed graph defining the workflow.

3. Wind farm optimization implementation

3.1. Problem formulation

The fast development of wind energy in recent decades has resulted in the proliferation of large wind farms. It has thus become an important yet challenging task to plan and design these wind farms, since many decisions need to be made and various engineering problems need to be solved with multi-disciplinary considerations [8]. Among the various tasks, wind farm layout optimization is a crucial one since it impacts the energy yield due to wake effects and also influences the cost of the wind farm, thus it has become an important field for both academia and industry [2, 9].

For a wind farm composed of N_{wt} wind turbines, its layout can be defined by their x and y coordinates, which can be denoted as:

$$\mathbf{L} = [\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{Y}] = [x_1, x_2, \dots, x_{N_{wt}}, y_1, y_2, \dots, y_{N_{wt}}] \quad (1)$$

For a given site, the wind condition is determined. Assuming the wind turbines in this wind farm are of a fixed type, the annual energy production (AEP) will depend on the selected layout of the wind farm, since the wake losses of the wind turbines will be a function of the layout. Thus, we can write the layout optimization problem to maximize AEP for a given wind farm as:

$$\max_{\mathbf{L}} \text{AEP}(\mathbf{L}) \quad (2)$$

In the context of layout optimization, AEP is usually computed using engineering wake models since this is computationally affordable for optimization purposes. For the sake of brevity, the detailed procedure of computing AEP of a given wind farm using an engineering wake model is not described here, but can be found in many papers, such as in [10]. In this paper, the task of modelling AEP is taken by using readily available tools, i.e., PyWake [6] developed at DTU (Technical University of Denmark) and FLORIS [7] developed at NREL (National Renewable Energy Laboratory). These two tools are

both open source and Python based wind farm simulation tools that implement different static engineering wake models, thus allowing fast computation of AEP for a given wind farm. They have been widely used in various wind farm design and control applications. Details on usages and implementations of these tools are referred to their websites.

Besides the objective function defined in Eq. (2), wind farm layout optimization problems also need to face different kinds of constraints and requirements, that may come from technical, environmental, economic, regulatory and other considerations. As a minimal set of constraints, the wind farm boundary and the minimal spacing requirements are typically included in many studies in this field. Thus, we also consider these two types of constraints.

Wind farm boundary is usually defined by the energy planning authority when opening bids for a wind farm project, which requires all wind turbines to be installed inside a specified area. In a general case, the boundary can be of any shape. But here we consider a simple case that the boundary is a circle defined by its centre $[x_{cen}, y_{cen}]$ and its radius R_{bdr} . Thus this constraint can be written as:

$$\sqrt{(x_i - x_{cen})^2 + (y_i - y_{cen})^2} \leq R_{bdr}, \quad \text{for } i = 1, 2, \dots, N_{wt} \quad (3)$$

Minimal spacing requirements are defined for any two turbines in the wind farm, requiring their mutual distances to be larger than a threshold value d_{min} , which are governed by:

$$\sqrt{(x_i - x_j)^2 + (y_i - y_j)^2} \geq d_{min}, \quad \text{for } i, j = 1, 2, \dots, N_{wt} \text{ and } i \neq j \quad (4)$$

Based on the definitions of these two kinds of constraints, we can then easily calculate the respective constraint violation degrees for the whole wind farm as:

$$Viol_{bdr} = \sum_{i=1}^{N_{wt}} \max\left(\sqrt{(x_i - x_{cen})^2 + (y_i - y_{cen})^2} - R_{bdr}, 0\right) \quad (5)$$

$$Viol_{spc} = \sum_{i=1}^{N_{wt}} \sum_{j=1, j \neq i}^{N_{wt}} \max\left(d_{min} - \sqrt{(x_i - x_j)^2 + (y_i - y_j)^2}, 0\right) \quad (6)$$

Note that the distance of a turbine to itself is of course not taken into account when calculating the violation degree with regards to the minimal spacing constraint as shown in Eq. (6). Then the total constraint violation degree of a given wind farm is a function of its layout that measures how much the layout violates the specified constraints:

$$Viol_{tot}(\mathbf{L}) = Viol_{bdr}(\mathbf{L}) + Viol_{spc}(\mathbf{L}) \quad (7)$$

For the constrained optimization problem defined in Eqs. (2-4), many algorithms for constrained optimization can be used to solve it. It can also be transformed into an unconstrained optimization problem using the penalty function method, which incorporates the constraint violation degree in the extended objective function. For the layout optimization problem we consider, it can be written as:

$$\min_{\mathbf{L}} f(\mathbf{L}) = \min_{\mathbf{L}} (-AEP(\mathbf{L}) + w \cdot Viol_{tot}(\mathbf{L})) \quad (8)$$

where w is a weighting parameter for the penalty term, which typically takes a large number in order to penalize the infeasible solutions, i.e., those violates the considered constraints.

Note that in the transformed optimization problem as defined in Eq. (8), the original maximization problem has been changed into a minimization problem of the new objective function $f(\mathbf{L})$, following the convention of many optimization tools and techniques.

3.2. Wind farm evaluation system

To solve the optimization problem defined in Eq. (8), optimization algorithms need to be used to iteratively propose new design(s), i.e., new layout(s) L_{new} , and evaluate the associated objective function(s). Traditionally, this requires running the wind farm simulation tool to calculate AEP and the constraint models to compute the total violation degree ($Viol_{tot}$). However, the computational effort for evaluating AEP is much higher than computing the constraint violation degree, and the infeasible layouts, i.e., those with positive values for $Viol_{tot}$, are in the end discarded in the optimization results. Therefore, the computation efforts used to calculate the AEP for these infeasible layouts are essentially wasted.

Considering these facts and following the similar principle behind the Random Search algorithm, an optimization method developed by Feng and Shen in [10] for wind farm layout optimization, we propose a new method for evaluating AEP of any new layouts in the optimization problem: computing the actual AEP with PyWake or FLORIS for feasible layouts and assigning the previous computed AEP value of a feasible layout to the infeasible layouts. The evaluation logic is governed by:

$$AEP(L_{new}) = \begin{cases} AEP(L_{new}), & \text{if } Viol_{tot}(L_{new}) \leq 0, \\ AEP(L_{pre}), & \text{if } Viol_{tot}(L_{new}) > 0. \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

where L_{pre} denotes the previous feasible layout with its AEP computed already, thus its AEP value has been recorded in the platform and can be directly used. Note that for our considered problem the difference in AEP between two candidate layouts will be relatively small, and the large weighting parameter w in the penalty term will always make the infeasible layout has a higher objective function than its feasible counterparts, thus the difference introduced by assigning the previous computed AEP value of another layout to a infeasible new layout has essentially no impact on the obtained optimization results.

Using the integration platform described in Section 2, we build a wind farm evaluation system that can compute the objective function for any wind farm layout with the AEP evaluation method described in Eq. (9). Four models are coupled in this system, which includes: a circular boundary constraint model and a minimal spacing constraint model that are in-house developed models written in Python following the standard model format, and PyWake model and FLORIS model wrapped into the standard model format. The composition of the System is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. A wind farm evaluation system based on the proposed integration platform that evaluates the objective function of a wind farm's layout.

Note that in this system, AEP computation is done by selecting one of the three trajectories marked by dashed lines, following the evaluation logic defined in Eq. (9). Whether to use PyWake and FLORIS model to compute AEP for a feasible layout depends on the setting of the parameters of the system.

3.3. Optimization methods

With the wind farm evaluation system in place, we can solve the layout optimization by coupling it to some optimization tools. In this study, we use an in-house optimization library that are written in Python and can be steadily used to solve optimization problems by coupling it to the objective function and constraint functions. The workflow of the general optimization process is depicted in Figure 4.

Figure 4. A typical workflow to solve the wind farm layout optimization problem.

Two optimization algorithms are used in this study. One is the Random Search (RS) algorithm, a single solution based search algorithm for solving constrained wind farm layout optimization problems. This algorithm was first developed by Feng and Shen in [10] for solving single objective layout optimization problem for uniform wind farms, i.e., wind farms composed of the same type of wind turbines. It was also later extended to non-uniform wind farms [9], multi-objective optimization [11] and has demonstrated better performances in comparison with several other algorithms [12]. The procedure of this algorithm is shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Random search algorithm for wind farm design optimization.

The other used algorithm is a type of Genetic Algorithm (GA). As a nature inspired population based meta-heuristic algorithm, GA is the most widely used algorithm in the literature of wind farm layout optimization [13], with most studies used binary coded GAs. A real-coded GA proposed by Chuang et al. [14] has been implemented in the in-house optimization library and used in this study. This version of GA was developed for constrained optimization using three specially designed evolutionary operators: ranking selection, direction-based crossover, and dynamic random mutation. It has shown a better performance than other traditional versions of GA for a variety of benchmark constrained optimization

problems in [14], where details of the algorithm can be found. Note that the recommended parameters suggested by the authors in [14] are used in this study.

4. Case study

As a case study to demonstrate the usage of the proposed platform, we apply the developed system for an offshore wind farm composed of 9 wind turbines. The type of the wind turbines is assumed to be the IEA 15 MW reference turbine [15], which has become a widely used large reference turbine. The rotor diameter of the turbine is 242.24 m and the hub height is 150 m.

The wind resource data for this wind farm is based on the Horns Rev 1 wind farm in Denmark, which has sector wise Weibull distribution parameters and wind rose data openly available in the literature. In this study, the data documented in [16] is extrapolated from the original reference height (62 m) to the intended hub height (150 m) with a wind shear coefficient of 0.12 assumed. The resulting wind rose of the site at 150 m is plotted in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Wind rose of the considered wind farm site at hub height (150 m).

The original layout of the wind farm is assumed to be a regular square shape and has a uniform spacing of 7.5 times of rotor diameters between rows and columns. The circular boundary of the wind farm is assumed to have a centre at the central turbine position and have a radius that just cover the 9 turbines. The original layout and the related boundary are shown in the left figure in Figure 7.

Figure 7. Original (left) and optimized (right) wind farm layouts with the boundary marked by the dashed lines.

For the PyWake model and FLORIS model, the same Gaussian shape wake model as developed in [17] is selected, and the same parameters for turbulence intensity (0.1) and wind shear coefficient (0.12) are assumed. Since the PyWake model is computationally faster than the FLORIS model, it is selected to be the AEP calculator during the optimization process, while FLORIS is used to re-evaluate some of the obtained and considered layouts. The weighting parameter in the penalty term is set as $w = 1000$. To have a fair comparison, 5 runs of each algorithms are conducted. In each run, the RS algorithm runs for 10000 steps, while the GA algorithm runs for 100 generation, which consists of also 10000 iterations in each run considering it uses a population size of 100. Out of the 10 runs, the best performing layout is from a RS run, which yields an AEP of 771.39 GWh as evaluated by PyWake and 767.65 GWh as evaluated by FLORIS, as shown in Figure 7.

As one can notice, the optimized layout has most turbines (8 out of 9) re-located on the edge of the wind farm boundary, and the AEP has increased by 0.41% based on PyWake estimates. Also the two different tools gives slightly different estimates on the AEP value of the same wind farm, which could be due to the different implementation details of the AEP assessment and wake modelling procedure.

Despite these differences in the estimated numbers, the re-evaluated evolutionary history as shown in Figure 8, i.e., re-evaluated AEP values of all the improved layouts in the optimization process, reveals in general very similar trends of the AEP evolution. This suggests that they in general agrees on which layout is better in terms of AEP, and they also estimate a similar relative increase of AEP for the optimized layout with regards to the optimized layout (0.41% in PyWake vs. 0.35% in FLORIS).

Figure 8. Evolution history of the best run of RS using the PyWake model (in blue) and re-evaluated in FLORIS (in orange).

Details of results for the 10 optimization runs are listed in Table 1, where the best runs are marked in bold text for both algorithms. Note that comparing to the total number of considered iterations (1000), the number of actual AEP calculations (N_{AEP}), i.e., those done by using PyWake following the method defined in Eq. (9), is usually much lower. This has the effect of reducing the consumed computational time and demonstrate the effectiveness of the proposed method.

To better compare the performance of these two algorithms, their evolution histories are plotted in parallel as shown in Figure 9. Note that in this figure, dashed lines represent runs of GA and solid lines represent RS runs, and in each generation of the GA optimization process, only the AEP of the best performing layout is plotted here. Comparing these histories, one can note that RS runs in general have better performance as they improved faster in a more gradual manner, even though some of the GA runs obtain slightly better layouts than some of the RS runs. Also it is clear that some of the GA runs suffer from pre-mature convergence and fail to obtain good optimized results.

Table 1. Summary of multiple runs of two optimization algorithms for the considered wind farm layout optimization problem ^a.

Run [#]	AEP _{opt} [GWh]	Increase [%]	Time [s]	N _{AEP} [-]	AEP _{opt} [GWh]	Increase [%]	Time [s]	N _{AEP} [-]
	GA (Genetic Algorithm)				RS (Random Search)			
1	771.14	0.38	283.8	5803	771.26	0.39	285.6	4629
2	771.18	0.38	265.9	4900	771.17	0.38	249.6	4622
3	769.92	0.22	353.1	6457	771.39	0.41	172.2	4531
4	770.42	0.28	428.3	6682	771.14	0.38	262.8	4514
5	768.46	0.03	15.4	97	771.32	0.40	286.5	4597

^a Note that the AEP values and the associated increase percentages are based on PyWake simulations. Computational times are recorded for running the optimization on a laptop with a single CPU. And N_{AEP} denotes the number of consumed AEP calculations.

Figure 9. Evolution histories of multiple runs of RS (in solid lines) and GA (in dashed lines).

5. Conclusions

This study described the design of a general tool chain integration platform for multi-disciplinary analysis and optimization in wind energy. This platform is written in Python and will be provided as an open source framework. The design of this platform puts emphasis on flexibility, usability and extensibility. General model classes with standard interfaces that can wrap custom tools/models in different formats and based on different programming languages will be provided, together with examples that are easy to understand and modify. Coupling tools/models into a system then becomes an easy task of connecting models by inputs and outputs and defining workflow with a directed graph.

The concept of the platform was described in this work together with an example of using the platform to development a wind farm layout optimization system by coupling existing wind farm simulations tools, self-written constraint models and optimization algorithms. To reduce the computational efforts, an evaluation procedure for AEP is also proposed by distinguishing feasible and infeasible layout and using previous computed AEP value for the infeasible layouts. The case study on a wind farm with 9 turbines demonstrated the usage and effectiveness of the developed platform. By easily coupling and switching different models/tools and algorithms, the platform can enable the wind

energy community to conduct more systematic benchmarking and comparison of models, tools and algorithms, which are very important to the advancement of wind energy science and technology.

This study describes the current status of the platform's first implementation. Future research and development efforts will be devoted to the further development of the platform together with more associated examples, which are targeted at more models/tools, more application scenarios for more potential academic and industrial users.

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